

Virtual Machine Details and Requirements

The image provided (SugarC.ova) was generated with Oracle's VirtualBox 6.1. The image is fitted with the operating system Ubuntu 16.04.7-server-amd, since this is a server distribution, there is no graphical interface. This environment was chosen specifically to make sure the execution environment is as similar to the machine used as possible (as described in our paper, we relied on specific system headers when evaluating SugarC). When the machine is loaded up, it currently uses about 9.9GB of space, if all tests are executed and not cleaned up, the space should amass to 30GB. The current cap is set to 64GB, so it should all be able to fit without modification. The virtual machine is initialized to 16GB of RAM. While we believe this is sufficient for most experiments, there may be issues that arise with the larger files in busybox and toybox (see detailed instructions below).

Assuming no modifications are being made, one should be able to run our experiments by simply importing the virtual machine image, logging in with username:sugarc password:sugarc and executing the .sh scripts.